
A STUDY ON OVERVIEW OF RURAL TRANSFORMATION IN SAMINATHAM

Dr.S.Kartheeswari, Assistant Professor of Commerce (CA) SF,

The Standard Fireworks Rajaratnam College for Women, Sivakasi.

kartheeswari-com@sfrcollege.edu.in, kartheeswari367@gmail.com

Mobile No. 9486118237

INTRODUCTION

Rural transformation is fundamental in understanding future food security and can be more formally defined as a long-term process of change in fundamental features of the way people in rural areas live and act economically, taking into consideration how they are embedded in societal and global dynamics. It is indicated by the following manner.

- The gap between per capita rural GDP and per capita national GDP.
- The gap between rural HDI and national HDI.
- The gap between the ratio of agricultural GDP / total GDP and the ratio of agricultural employment / total employment.

CAUSES OF RURAL TRANSFORMATION

The push and pull factors are behind the rural to urban migration. The push factors that force people to move out of villages for poverty and lack of basic amenities. Higher education, increased standard of living, more job opportunities and wages are the pull factors that attracted by the people to move from villages to cities.

STRATEGIES FOR RURAL DEVELOPMENT

The objectives of rural development revolve around the progress in rural economy and raise the standard of living of the rural people. Education, entrepreneurship, physical infrastructure and social infrastructure are playing the vital role in developing rural regions. The three linked pillars of rural development are social, economic and environmental factors. These

three factors are interconnected for supporting the rural communities in order to enhanced sustainability and long-term well-being. The strategies for rural development are mainly focused as hereunder.

1. Alleviation of poverty.
2. Providing better livelihood opportunities for rural population.
3. Improvement of infrastructure facilities.
4. Providing basic amenities such as housing, sanitation etc.
5. Agricultural development and livelihood diversification.
6. Social inclusion and empowerment.
7. Environmental sustainability.
8. Governance and institutional reforms.

FACTORS OF RURAL DEVELOPMENT

The following are the factors of rural development.

1. Geographical location
2. Size of village
3. Productivity of land
4. Type of land use
5. Active population
6. Popular production areas
7. Proximity to a river
8. Housing comfort
9. Characteristics of drinking water
10. Productive fruit areas
11. Co-operativization

12. Social dimensions

CHALLENGES OF RURAL DEVELOPMENT

There are three major challenges in rural development. They are bringing about economic development, developing facilities to meet social needs and finally bringing about a change of attitude in matters concerning society, culture and ways of thinking.

Tamil Nadu Rural Transformation Project is an emerging concept for promoting rural enterprises, access to finance and employment opportunities in the selected blocks of Tamil Nadu. Besides, our government highlighted that Rural Enterprise Ecosystem Development, seeks to create an enabling environment for promoting and strengthening enterprises and jobs in the target areas through identifying market and value-chain strengthening opportunities, supporting the development of favourable business conditions, and informing pathways to effective and efficient business enterprise development. Our government helps to uplift the skills and job opportunities of people residing in rural area. Moreover, our government aims to sustainable wage and self-employment opportunities promote relevant skills for higher value agriculture and allied activities, and nonfarm activities and enable entrepreneurship through market responsive skills and entrepreneurship development. This project is led by the Department of Rural Development & Panchayat Raj, Government of Tamil Nadu.

It enlightened and induced the researcher to make the study to know the rural transformation of people residing in Saminatham.

PROFILE OF SAMINATHAM

The total geographical area of such village is 1520 hectares. According to Census 2020, the total population of Saminatham 2999 and there are about 645 houses.

SAMPLING DESIGN

The survey was based on a questionnaire consisting of 115 questions covering the complete details of a family like personal information, savings habit, land details, Electrical and electronic appliances have, loan borrowed details, usage of government schemes, drainage and toilet facility, entrepreneurial skill and infrastructure facilities.

Therefore, the researcher used Raosoft Sample Size Calculator for making the study of population in the rural transformation development. Such calculator advised that the sample size would need to be 341 with a confidence level of 50% significance. Therefore, the researcher makes an attempt to study the sample size of 341 adopted convenience sampling method.

FACTORS INFLUENCING RURAL TRANSFORMATION OF SAMINATHAM

Table 1: Educational Qualification

S. No	Educational Qualification	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Illiterate	48	14.08
2.	Up to 10 th Standard	110	32.26
3.	Up to 12 th Standard	130	38.12
4.	Graduate	53	15.54
Total		341	100.00

The study area consists of eight schools and only one school in Poovanathapuram is having a higher secondary education. 38.12 per cent of the people are having their education status up to 12th standard in school level; 32.26 per cent of them are studied up to 10th standard; 15.54 per cent of them are graduates and the rest 14.08 per cent of them are illiterate. They said that only one higher secondary school is having in the nearest. So they have troubled to continue their higher studies. Some of them only moved to Sivakasi and

Srivilliputtur for higher studies. Therefore, they need middle and higher school in their area for their betterment in life.

Table 2: Annual Income

S. No	Annual Income	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Before ₹ 50000	64	18.77
2.	₹ 50001 - ₹ 100000	175	51.32
3.	Above ₹ 100000	102	29.91
Total		341	100.00

Nearly Half of the respondents 175 (51.32%) are earning an annual income range between ₹ 50,001 and ₹ 1,00,000; 102(29.91%) of them are earning an annual income as above the range of ₹ 1,00,000 and the rest 64 (18.77%) of them are only earning an annual income below ₹ 50,000. Majority (70%) of them is treated as below the poverty line category and mostly they suffered from poor condition in agricultural trade practices. So, they prefer to move forward to another job like 100 days job opportunity plan, fireworks, painters, printers and so on. These job opportunities are also becoming down. So, their earning capacity is reduced and they gave suggestions to the government for improving their annual income through such jobs, government subsidies and credit schemes pertaining to the field of agriculture and start-ups.

Table 3: Savings Habit

S. No	Savings Habit	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Yes	239	70.09
2.	No	102	29.91
Total		341	100.00

Two-third (70%) of the people is having the habit of savings in SBI, IOB, TMB and so on. Only 30% of them are unaware of the savings habit and they did not open any account on banks. So, they need become aware about Pradhan Mantri Jan-Dhan Yojana (P.M.J.D.Y) for their betterment in future like deposits, remittance, credit, insurance, pension in an affordable manner.

Table 4: Details of Own Land

S. No	Details of Own Land	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Yes	226	66.28
2.	No	115	33.72
Total		341	100.00

As per our survey, 66.28 per cent of the people are having own land and the rest of them are not having the land.

Table 5: Details of Own House Property

S. No	Details of House Property	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Owned	223	65.39
2.	Rented	118	34.61
Total		341	100.00

65.39 per cent of the people are living in their own house and the rest (34.61%) of them are living in rented house.

Table 6: Number of Facilities Availed

S. No	Number of Facilities Availed in a house	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Up to 3	85	24.93
2.	4-6	206	60.41

3.	Above 6	50	14.66
Total		341	100.00

Nearly 60% of the people are felt comfortable with the usage of Free Mixi, grinder, Fan, laptop, cycle and motor cycle from the government; 25% of them are using free mixi, grinder and fan; 14.66 % of them are availed more than six facilities offered by our government.

Table 7: Details of Ration Card

S. No	Details of Ration Card	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Green	223	65.39
2.	White	88	25.81
3.	Yellow	30	8.80
Total		341	100.00

65.39% of the people are having green colour ration card and they are enjoying purchasing of rice, wheat, dhal and oil in an affordable prices; 25% of them are having white ration card and the rest 8.80% of them only having yellow card.

Table 8: Details of Interest of the Respondents to become an Entrepreneur

S. No	To become an Entrepreneur	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Yes	278	81.52
2.	No	63	18.48
Total		341	100.00

Nearly two-third of the people (81.52 per cent) is struggling in running their family due to earning constraints in the poor condition of agriculture and fireworks business. So, they wanted to become an entrepreneur and they are basically having some idea about silk thread, paper quelling, tailoring, art and craft; only 18.48 per cent of them are not having an idea to start-up the business. At present, sericulture, mushroom cultivation and vermicompost are becoming

popular and earning high income. So, they need such orientation programme for earning high income with minimum risk and capital in their own places.

Table 9: Details on Area of Interest to become an Entrepreneur

S. No	Nature of Work to be undertaken	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Sericulture	96	34.53
2.	Mushroom Cultivation	90	32.37
3.	Vermicompost	62	22.30
4.	Tailoring	20	7.19
5.	Handicrafts	10	3.61
Total		278	100.00

Out of 278 interested respondents, 34.53 per cent of the people are interesting to start sericulture business; 32.37 per cent of them are interesting to do mushroom cultivation business; 22.30 per cent of them are going to start vermicompost business because these activities basically active in relating to the agricultural produce and continuous increase in earning; 7.19 per cent of them are interesting to start tailoring business with their skills and the balance 3.61 per cent of them to do art and handicrafts as unique in nature.

Table 10: Number of Loan Taken

S. No	Number of Loan Taken	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Single Loan	289	84.75
2.	More than one loan	52	15.25
Total		341	100.00

As per our survey, all the people are taken the loan from private and public sector banks and individuals. Majority 85 per cent of them are taken only one loan either for housing loan, marriage loan, medical loan, educational loan, vehicle loan, business loan and so on. Only 15

per cent of them borrowed more than one loan in order to meet their contingencies in family and business.

Table 11: Details of Drainage Facility

S. No	Drainage Facility	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Yes	261	76.54
2.	No	80	23.46
Total		341	100.00

76.54 per cent of the people are using drainage facility for cleanliness and 23.46 per cent of them are not having the drainage facility. So, they need drainage to become healthy.

Table 12: Details of Toilet Facility

S. No	Toilet Facility	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Yes	277	81.23
2.	No	64	18.77
Total		341	100.00

81.23 per cent of the people are having own toilet in their houses and they are using neatly for becoming more healthy and hygienic and the rest 18.77 per cent of them are not having the toilet in their houses. So, they have to become an aware of Swachh Bharat (Sanitation Schemes) especially for Open Defecation free.

Table 13: Details of Sickness faced

S. No	Nature of Sickness	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Fever	59	26.46
2.	Headache	25	11.21
3.	Leg pain	12	5.38
5.	Cold, cough	57	25.56

7.	Heart Attack	22	9.87
8.	Blood Pressure	10	4.48
9.	Diabetics	14	6.28
10.	TB & Cancer	24	10.76
Total		223	100.00

As per our survey 223 from the out of 341 people are suffered either from fever or blood pressure, diabetics, cold and so on. Only 35 per cent (118 respondents) of them are felt well. Out of such 59 people, 26.46 per cent of them affected from severe fever; 25.56 per cent of them suffered from cold and cough; 11.21 per cent of them suffered from headache; 10.76 per cent of them affected from TB and cancer; 9.87 per cent of them affected from heart attack, 6.28 per cent of them affected diabetics; 5.38 per cent of them suffered from leg pain and the rest 4.48 per cent of them suffered from blood pressure. As per such detail, they need diabetics' checkup, cancer checkup, dental and general medical camp in the forthcoming years to create the healthy people.

Table 14: Details of Tree Plantation Awareness

S. No	Tree Plantation Facility – Good for Health	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Yes	298	87.39
2.	No	43	12.61
Total		341	100.00

Nearly 90 per cent of the people are having an aware about tree plantation and the rest 10 per cent of them are an unaware about Green India.

Table 15: Details of Open Defecation Awareness

S. No	Open Toilet – Injurious to Health	No. of Respondents	Percentage
-------	-----------------------------------	--------------------	------------

1.	Yes	277	81.23
2.	No	64	18.77
Total		341	100.00

Nearly 80 per cent of the people are aware about the own defecation and its problems and the rest 20 per cent of them are unaware about open defecation and how it creates the problems regarding the health of the people. So, government has to create clean India and green India awareness by dramas and rallies through NSS Volunteers and Unnat Bharat Abhiyan activities.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

- 38.12% of the people are having their education status up to 12th standard in school level.
- Nearly Half of the respondents 175 (51.32%) are earning an annual income range between ₹ 50,001 and ₹ 1,00,000;
- Two-third (70%) of the people is having the habit of savings in SBI, IOB and so on.
- 66.28 per cent of the people are having own land.
- 65.39 per cent of the people are living in their own house.
- Nearly 60 per cent of the people are felt comfortable with the usage of Free Mixi, grinder, Fan, laptop, cycle and motor cycle from the government.
- Majority 223 (65.39%) of the people are having green colour ration card.
- Nearly two-third of the people (278) is struggling in running their family due to earning constraints in the poor condition of agriculture and fireworks business. So, they wanted to become an entrepreneur.
- Sericulture, mushroom cultivation and vermicompost businesses are active in relating to the agricultural produce and continuous increase in earning.
- All the people taken the loan from private and public sector banks and individuals.

-
- Majority 85 per cent of them are taken only one loan either for housing loan, marriage loan, medical loan, educational loan, vehicle loan, business loan and so on.
 - 23.46 per cent of the people are not having the drainage facility.
 - 18.77 per cent of the people are not having the toilet facility in their houses.
 - As per our survey 223 from the out of 341 people are suffered either from fever or blood pressure, diabetics, cold and so on.
 - Nearly 87 per cent of the people are having an aware about tree plantation.
 - The people of Saminatham village gave water to such saplings by 100 days job opportunity plan.
 - 18.77 per cent of the people are unaware about open defecation.

SUGGESTIONS TO THE RURAL TRANSFORMATION DEVELOPMENT

- To increase the literacy level in the study area, two or three higher secondary schools and one library should be originated by the government.
- In order to develop the annual income, government subsidies and credit schemes pertaining to the field of agriculture and start-ups as and when required without any delay and discriminations.
- To make an aware about Pradhan Mantri Jan-Dhan Yojana (P.M.J.D.Y) for their betterment in future like deposits, remittance, credit, insurance, pension in an affordable manner.
- To require common assembly hall in their college for celebrating any personal functions.
- To require Primary Health Centre in the eve of any illness on emergency.
- To require ATM Counter.
- To conduct regular medical camp like general, diabetics, dental, breast cancer.
- To improve the drainage facility.
- To require Industrial Estate for getting regular earnings and their economic development.

-
- To conduct some orientation programme for earning high income with minimum risk and capital in their own places.
 - To conduct guest lecture relating to the area of banking and insurance for the welfare of the people especially for farmers.
 - To organize any workshop for online fund transfer, online upload the documents and how to avail the government schemes via online with the help of any Private or Public Sector Banks and Insurance Companies.
 - To offer any orientation programme or workshop for improving the entrepreneurial skills of the people and survive them in a competitive era.
 - To increase the bus facility especially from Sivakasi, Srivilliputtur and Rajapalayam.
 - To create an aware of Swachh Bharat (Sanitation Schemes) especially for Open Defecation free and its problems.

CONCLUSION

From this survey, the researcher received lot of information and they move friendly and they also gave their needs also. Mostly, these needs were the valuable one. People of Saminatham required Higher Secondary School, Primary Health Centre, ATM Counter, Agriculture Development regarding seeds; water subsidy etc. Sericulture, Mushroom Cultivation and Vermicompost programme was organized for helping the farmers and inmates of Saminatham to get aware of self-employment in the growing field of sericulture, mushroom cultivation and vermicompost. Besides, after the session completed people gave the feedback. In this feedback, they said that these two programmes was highly helpful, motivated to become start-ups and also to earn within a house.

References

I. Books

1. Thomas G. Fraser (2013), "India's Rural Transformation and Development", Suryodaya Books, New Delhi, 1st Edition
2. Ritesh Chatterjee and Dipali Saha (2022), "Social Transformation in Rural India", Global Vision Publishing House, New Delhi, 1st Edition

II. Website

1. <https://geoiq.io/places/saminatham/gfeQTFgWeG>
2. <https://www.scribd.com/document/496612045/2-2-AGRICULTURAL-TRANSFORMATION-and-RURAL-DEVELOPMENT-2#:~:text=and%20Rural%20Development>

